

SIMULATION METHODS FOR HIGH-CYCLE FATIGUE-DRIVEN DELAMINATION USING COHESIVE ZONE MODELS – FUNDAMENTAL BEHAVIOR AND BENCHMARK STUDIES

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ABSTRACT

A novel computational method for simulating fatigue-driven delamination cracks in composite laminated structures under cyclic loading based on a cohesive zone model [2] and new benchmark studies with four other comparable methods [3-6] are presented. The benchmark studies describe and compare the traction-separation response in the cohesive zone and the transition phase from quasi-static to fatigue loading for each method. Furthermore, the accuracy of the predicted crack growth rate is studied and compared for each method. It is shown that the method described in [2] is significantly more accurate than the other methods [3-6]. Finally, studies are presented of the dependency and sensitivity to the change in different quasi-static material parameters and model specific fitting parameters. It is shown that all the methods except [2] rely on different parameters which are not possible to determine experimentally and/or depend on the problem and are therefore not possible to determine in advance which is needed in order to do predictive simulation studies.

1 INTRODUCTION

One of the governing failure mechanisms in layered composite materials is fatigue driven delaminations. Thus, much attention has been given to the topic within recent years both with regard to experimental characterization and simulation methods, but there are still many unanswered questions [1]. The low level of knowledge and maturity of simulation methods generally mean that verifying the fatigue strength for a composite structural design is done by fatigue testing on the full structure or larger substructural parts which in both cases are time consuming and costly. Therefore, there is a large potential for a cost reduction by relying more on verification through simulation and less on testing. A first step to meet this potential is to investigate the characteristics in regard to reliability and predictive capabilities of the existing methods for fatigue-driven delamination simulation.

This work presents a study on the fundamental behavior and benchmark studies of five of the recent simulation methods [2-6] falling in the category of methods for high-cycle fatigue-driven delaminations based on cohesive zone models [1]. It is shown that there is a large difference in the accuracy and behavior of each model and that some of the methods are very inaccurate.

2 COHESIVE MODELS FOR FATIGUE AND QUASI-STATIC LOADING

The models considered in this work [2-6] all apply the envelope load approach. This means that only the envelope of the cyclic variation of the load on the structure is modelled and not the full cyclic variation, see Fig. [1]. The envelope load modelling approach is the best suited approach for high-cycle simulations as simulations using models that rely on the complete cyclic variation of the crack face separation are too computationally inefficient [1].

Figure 1: Envelope load model approach exemplified by a cyclic moment M loaded DCB specimen [2].

Common for all the models is that the development of damage is described by a damage rate formulation dD/dN , where D is a damage parameter and N is the number of load cycles. The damage parameter D is defined differently in some of the models, but common for all the models is that the damage parameter governs the relation between cohesive tractions. Furthermore, all the models included in this benchmark study are based on a bilinear quasi-static cohesive zone model, see Figure 2.

Figure 2: A bilinear cohesive law for quasi-static crack growth simulations for pure mode I crack separation where (δ_o, τ_o) is the point at onset of damage, K is the initial stiffness, and δ_c is the critical separation at which there is full damage and the cohesive tractions are reduced to zero.

The damage rate formulations considered here are shown in Table 1.

Authors	Damage rate models dD/dN
Bak et al. [2]	$\left(F_\beta \frac{\partial \beta}{\partial a} + F_\lambda \frac{\partial \lambda}{\partial a} \right) P(G)$
Turon et al. [3]	$\frac{1}{a_{cz}} \frac{(\delta_c(1-D) + D\delta_o)^2}{\delta_c\delta_o} P(w_{tot})$
Robinson et al. [4]	$\frac{C_1}{1+C_3} e^{C_2 D} \delta^{1+C_3}$
Pirondi and Moroni [5]	$\frac{1}{a_{cz}} P(G)$
Harper and Hallet [6]	$\frac{1 - D_s - D_{f,u}}{a_{fat}} P(w_{tot})$

Table 1: Damage rate models.

Only a few details of each model will be presented here. For a more elaborated description of the models the reader is referred to the individual papers describing the models and the recent review on fatigue driven delaminations [1]. The models of [2,5] are functions of any of the common Paris' law variants on the form $P(G) := da/dN = f(\Delta G, G_m, \varphi)$ where ΔG and G_m are the amplitude and mean of the energy release rate, respectively and $\varphi = G_{II}/(G_I + G_{II})$ is the mode mixity expressed in mode decomposed energy release rates G_I and G_{II} . The models of [3,6] are depending on a function inspired by Paris' law variants, but instead of being a function of the cyclic varying energy release rate these models are functions of the cyclic variation of the total specific work at each point in the cohesive interface $P(w_{tot}) := da/dN = f(\Delta w_{tot}, w_{tot,m}, \omega)$ where Δw_{tot} and $w_{tot,m}$ are the amplitude and mean of the total specific work at each point in the cohesive interface, respectively and $\omega = w_{tot,II}/(w_{tot,I} + w_{tot,II})$ is the mode mixity expressed in mode decomposed total specific work at each point in the cohesive interface $w_{tot,I}$ and $w_{tot,II}$. This approach implies that there is a different da/dN value for all points in the cohesive zone which can be difficult to interpret physically, but it provides the nice advantage over the models of [2,5] that there is no need for determining the energy release rate using for example the J -integral approach [8]. The models of [3,6] assume that the material parameters of the experimentally obtained Paris' law variant on the form $da/dN = f(\Delta G, G_m, \varphi)$ can be used in the $da/dN = f(\Delta w_{tot}, w_{tot,m}, \omega)$ formulation. The model of [4] is different from the other models in the sense that it does not rely on parameters, e.g. Paris' law parameters, which can be determined experimentally. Instead the parameters C_1 , C_2 and C_3 are to be determined in a trial and error approach by fitting the overall simulated response of a structure to experimentally determined crack growth rate data.

3 DESCRIPTION OF THE BENCHMARK STUDIES

For all the studies on the fundamental behavior of each damage rate model and the benchmark studies the so-called cylinder model [7] is used. The cylinder model consists of a rigid cylinder rolling on a flat rigid surface with cohesive spring elements connecting the surface of the cylinder and the flat surface on the left side of the contact point, see Figure 3. The cylinder model provides a simple approach to perform parameter studies for pure mode I fatigue driven delamination as well as to isolate and compare certain properties of the fatigue damage rate models. The model has been implemented as a finite element program in Matlab and an incremental moment controlled solution procedure is used.

Figure 3: The cylinder model.

The following studies have been conducted and are presented in Section 4:

1. Traction distribution during fatigue driven crack propagation: τ vs. δ .
2. Transition response from quasi-static to fatigue propagation: simulated da/dN vs. a .
3. Shape of the simulated Paris' law and error: Simulated da/dN vs. G/G_c and error vs. G/G_c .
4. Influence of the cylinder radius which mimics the sensitivity of local stiffness changes in real structures due to e.g. changing thickness of the surrounding layers: R vs. error.
5. The influence of the magnitude of the onset traction τ_o and initial stiffness K of the quasi-static cohesive law.

The parameters used in the simulations are shown in Table 3.

Parameter	value
G_{Ic}	0.26 N/mm
τ_{I0}	30 MPa
K	10^6 N/mm ³
C_I	$3.08 \cdot 10^{-3}$
m_I	5.4
R	100 mm
L_e	0.05 mm
a_{cz} for $G = G_{Ic}$	1.86 mm
Δa_{target}	0.05 mm

Table 3: Quasi-static properties, fatigue properties and cylinder model settings common for all the studies presented unless otherwise stated [3, 9, 10].

The Paris' law variant which is used to represent the experimental crack growth rate data from [10] for pure mode I separation is given as:

$$\frac{da}{dN} = C_I \left(\frac{\Delta G}{G_c} \right)^{m_I} \quad (1)$$

The error estimation of all the results presented in Section 4 is done relatively to the value obtained with Equation (1). The simulated crack growth rate is determined as the slope of a linear fit to the last 50% of crack growth in order to filter out the influence of the initial transition phase.

The model specific parameters used in the studies are shown in Table 4.

Authors	Model specific parameters
Bak et al. [2]	none
Turon et al. [3]	a_{cz} is measured during simulation and the value used is reduced to 25%, $\Delta D_{max} = 10^{-5}$
Robinson et al. [4]	$C_I = 3 \cdot 10^{-3}$, $C_2 = 0.5$, $C_3 = 2$
Pirondi and Moroni [5]	a_{cz} is measured during simulation
Harper and Hallet [6]	a_{cz} in quasi-static 1.86 mm 50% of the cohesive zone develops fatigue damage.

Table 4: Model specific parameters used in the presented simulation results.

4 RESULTS

4.1 Fundamental behavior

The resulting cohesive law, traction vs. separation, during fatigue crack propagation has been simulated for all the damage rate models and is presented in Figure 4. The traction-separation relations shown in the graphs have been recorded for a single point in the interface which is located just in front of the cohesive zone after the quasi-static ramping phase, cf. Figure 1. Thus the traction-separation relation shown is the pure fatigue behavior as predicted by each model.

Figure 4: Results for the resulting cohesive law during fatigue crack propagation. The grey area represents the energy release rate $G/G_c = 0.5$.

The transition phase and delay of the simulated crack growth rate for each damage rate model are shown in Figure 5. The simulations have been conducted for 100 crack increments which is equivalent to an expected 5 mm crack growth according to the used Paris' law and the used crack increment length target Δa_{target} . However, the simulation using the model of [5] was terminated due to a highly overpredicted crack growth rate after approximately 30 mm crack growth.

Figure 5: Results of da/dN vs. crack length which demonstrates the difference in the transition phase of the simulated crack growth rate for each damage rate model. The simulations have been conducted with an energy release rate $G/G_c = 0.5$. The first 1 mm crack growth occurs due to the quasi-static ramping phase.

4.2 Performance and benchmark studies

As mentioned previously all the models are either dependent on Paris' law variants or fitted to da/dN vs. G/G_c data, thus it is relevant to study the methods ability to reproduce the da/dN vs. G/G_c behavior. This is shown in Figure 6 and the error for each simulation is shown in Table 5. A study with $K = 10^3 \text{ N/mm}^3$ has been included for the damage rate model [5] as this is how the results using the model was originally presented. However, this value of K is so low that meaningful simulation is not possible due to an artificially high compliant cohesive interface.

G/G_c	0.2	0.3	0.4	0.5	0.6	0.7	0.8	0.9
Bak et al. [2]	0.00 %	0.00 %	0.00 %	0.00 %	0.00 %	0.01 %	0.01 %	0.01 %
Turon et al. [3]	51.14 %	-4.79 %	-33.09 %	-50.42 %	-62.3 %	-70.04 %	-74.85 %	-77.09 %
Robinson et al. [4]	-40.96 %	-50.27 %	-51.44 %	-47.61 %	-37.95 %	-18.03 %	28.15 %	195.80 %
Pirondi and Moroni [5]	12200 %	19200 %	27300 %	36700 %	47900 %	62100 %	80000 %	112000 %
Harper and Hallet [6]	-37.01 %	-42.67 %	-46.23 %	-48.34 %	-49.3 %	-48.97 %	-46.81 %	-40.33 %

Table 5: Error data corresponding to the graphs shown in Figure 6.

Figure 6: Simulation results showing the methods ability to reproduce the da/dN vs. G/G_c behavior.

4.3 Dependencies

All the models except [2] rely on different parameters (fitting parameters) which are not possible to determine experimentally and/or depend on the problem and are therefore not possible to determine in advance which is a requirement for conducting predictive simulation studies. In Tab. [6] a qualitative overview of the parameters is given for each model. The parameters are divided into three categories: *Fitting parameters* included in the fatigue damage rate model, *quasi-static law parameters* and *other parameters*. By qualitative overview is meant that the presented conclusions are based on numerical studies, but due to limited space available the raw data is not presented. The number of arrows \uparrow next to each parameter indicates how sensitive each model is to that particular parameter. The more arrows are shown the higher is the sensitivity for that particular parameter.

Authors	Fitting parameters	Quasi-static law parameters	Other parameters
Bak et al. [2]	None	None	None
Turon et al. [3]	↑The cohesive zone length a_{cz} during fatigue.	↑ τ_{10} , ↑ K	↑↑ ΔD_{max}
Robinson et al. [4]	The material parameters for fatigue C_1 , C_2 and C_3	↑↑ τ_{10} ↑↑ K	Cylinder radius, R
Pirondi and Moroni [5]	↑The cohesive zone length a_{cz} during fatigue.	↑↑ τ_{10} , ↑↑ K	None
Harper and Hallet [6]	The cohesive zone length a_{cz} during fatigue. ↑The relation between the fatigue and quasi-static part of the cohesive zone length during fatigue.	None	The length of the cohesive zone a_{cz} during quasi-static crack growth.

Table 6: Qualitative overview of the parameters influencing the fatigue response of each of the damage rate models.

5 DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSION

The studies on the traction-separation behavior show that the overall response of each model is not the same in the sense that the response is close to the quasi-static law for small separations and that the traction-separation relation has a rapid decreasing tendency when the separation approaches the separation δ_G which fulfill that $\int_0^{\delta_G} \tau d\delta = G$. Since all the studied models are aimed at simulation of fatigue-driven delaminations the small differences in the traction-separation behavior seem of minor importance. Common for all the models is that the overall traction-separation behavior implies that the cohesive zone length during fatigue crack propagation is shorter than during quasi-static crack growth which means that there in general is a need for smaller elements for fatigue simulations compared to quasi-static simulations.

The error estimation of the ability to reproduce the crack growth rate shows that all the models except [2] produce significant errors both in terms of the slope and offset of the simulated Paris curve. It can be argued that the model of [4] is different than the others in the way that it does not assume or enforce a log-linear behavior (Paris' law) and the error estimation should therefore be done for the raw da/dN vs. G/G_c instead of the idealized Paris' law.

It has been shown that all the models except [2] are influenced by parameters not directly linked to the damage rate model. For all the models this behavior cannot be determined in advance which therefore significantly influence the capabilities as a tool for predictive simulations. This fact combined with the insignificant error produced in the studies using the model of [2] mean that the model of [2] is significantly ahead in terms of robustness and accuracy and is therefore the most promising method in regards to reach a predictive simulation tool for fatigue-driven delaminations.

Ongoing work is done on the characterization of the accuracy and computational efficiency of each model. Furthermore, studies are planned to further test the robustness of the methods in relation to conducting predictive simulations where fitting of parameters is not allowed.

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